

**Murrayazolinol—A Minor Carbazole
Alkaloid from *Murraya koenigii* Spreng.**

L. BHATTACHARYYA, S. K. CHATTERJEE, SHYAMALI ROY
and

D. P. CHAKRABORTY*

Bose Institute, 98/1, A. P. O. Road, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 27 June 1988, revised 7 November 1988,
accepted 18 November 1988

IN continuation of our investigations on carbazole alkaloids of *Murraya koenigii* Spreng.¹, we report the isolation and structure of a new minor constituent, named murrayazolinol from the root bark of the plant. Murrayazolinol (1) C₂₈H₂₈NO₂ [M⁺ 347], m.p. 290° was found homogeneous by tlc. With concentrated sulphuric acid it showed an abrupt colour change from red to green, and with concentrated sulphuric acid and acetic acid it gave a violet colouration.

The ir spectrum of murrayazolinol (1) showed the presence of OH or NH function (3 360), aromatic system (1 650, 1 620) and C—Me (1 380, 1 350 cm⁻¹) grouping. The uv spectrum of 1 showed the presence of a 2-oxygenated carbazole chromophoric system (λ_{max} (EtOH) 245, 265, 305 nm; log ε 4.85, 4.32, 4.40) closely similar to that of murrayazoline (2). The nmr spectrum of 1 showed the presence of a *gem*-dimethyl group (δ 1.93 and 1.5; 3H each, s), a methyl on an oxygen-bearing tetra-substituted carbon (δ 1.3; 3H), an aromatic methyl (δ 2.34; 3H, s), a benzylic proton (δ 3.33; 1H, br) and the carbinyl hydrogen of a secondary alcohol (δ 3.8; dd, *J* 7.2Hz). The spectrum also showed signals for five aromatic hydrogens of which the C-4 hydrogen appeared as a singlet at δ 7.50, the C-5 hydrogen as double doublet at δ 7.95 (*J* 7, 1Hz) and the remaining three hydrogens as a complex multiplet at δ 7.15–7.40. Further, it was observed that with the lone exception of the double doublet at δ 3.80, the spectrum of 1 is strikingly similar to that of murrayazoline (2). Like murrayazoline it also showed the absence of NH proton signal.

The mass spectrum of 1 showed a molecular ion peak at *m/z* 347 yielding significant ionic species (3–6) at *m/z* 332, 314, 248 and 210. The ionic species at *m/z* 332, formed by loss of a methyl group, gives rise to the ion peak by elimination of elements of water involving the secondary hydroxyl and a *trans*-hydrogen on the vicinal carbon. This is further supported by the peaks at *m/z* 248 and 210 which could arise from a dihydropyran system after elimination of C₈ unit containing the hydroxyl group constituting the cyclohexane ring with *gem*-dimethyl group.

Compared to the benzylic hydrogen signals of murrayazolinine (7) and isomurrayazolinine (8) which appear respectively at δ 3.68 and 3.83, the corresponding hydrogen signal of murrayazolinol like (2) appears at a higher field and this observation

rules out the proximity of the secondary hydroxyl group to the benzylic carbon. Based on this finding and the observed splitting pattern of the carbinyl hydrogen signal at δ 3.80, the hydroxyl group was placed on a carbon adjacent to oxygen-linked carbon atom of the pyran ring and the structure of murrayazolinol was advanced as 1.

1 Murrayazolinol; R=OH
2 Murrayazoline; R=H

3 *m/z* 382

4 *m/z* 314

5 *m/z* 248

6 *m/z* 210

7 Murrayazolinine; R₁=OH, R₂=H
8 Isomurrayazolinine; R₁=H, R₂=OH

Experimental

Isolation of murrayazolinol (1): Air-dried powdered stem bark of *Murraya koenigii* Spreng. was Soxhleted with benzene for 72 h. On removal of the solvent the resulting dry residue was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over Brockman's alumina. Fractions were collected in 100 ml portions eluting with appropriate solvents. Fractions eluted with benzene (18–22 fractions) yielded a solid, m.p. 290° (Found: C, 70.43; H, 7.45; N, 4.3; O, 4.46. C₂₈H₂₈NO₂ requires: C, 79.53; H, 7.20; O, 4.01%); it gave a picrate, m.p. 335°.

Picrate of 1: A solution of murrayazolinol (1; 20 mg) and picric acid in dry benzene (10 ml) was slowly evaporated on a water-bath. Crystals that appeared were filtered and recrystallised from dry benzene, m.p. 335° (Found: N, 9.50. C₂₈H₂₈N₂O₆ requires: N, 9.2%).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. B. B. Biswas, Director, Bose Institute and Prof. P. Chakrabarti, Chairperson, Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute for encouragement. The financial support to one of the authors (S.R.) by I.C.A.R. is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Fortschr. Chem. Org. Naturst.*, 1977, 34, 299; L. BHATTACHARYYA, S. K. ROY and D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Phytochemistry*, 1982, 21, 2482.
2. J. BORDNER, D. P. CHAKRABORTY, B. K. CHOWDHURY, S. N. GANGULY, K. O. DAS and B. WEINSTEIN, *Experientia*, 1972, 28, 1406.
8. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, S. N. GANGULY, P. N. MAJI, A. R. MITRA, K. O. DAS and B. WEINSTEIN, *Chem. Ind.*, 1973, 822.

Chemical Examination of Stem Bark of *Ficus infectoria* Roxb.

K. D. SWAMI, G. S. MALIK and N. P. S. BISHT*

Department of Chemistry, J. V. College, Baraut-250 611

Manuscript received 9 September 1987, revised 26 October 1988,
accepted 18 November 1988

FICUS infectoria Roxb. (Moraceae) is widely distributed in plains and lower hills of India. The stem bark of the plant is used^{1,2} in the indigenous system of medicine in the treatment of various diseases. We now report the isolation of some acetates of long-chain alcohols, methyl ricinolate, β -sitosterol, lanosterol, caffeic acid, bergenin and some sugars.

Experimental

The powdered stem bark was Soxhleted successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), benzene and alcohol (95%). The petroleum ether extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and chromatographed over neutral alumina. Elutions were carried out with petroleum ether and its mixture with benzene furnished the compounds A, B, C and D.

Compound A: Elution with petroleum ether yielded a white solid (MeOH : EtOAc), m.p. 60–70°. Tlc examination showed it to be a mixture of four components. The glc and mass spectra^{3,4} revealed these as n-tetracosyl acetate (M^+ 396, 37.1%), n-hexacosyl acetate (M^+ 424, 15.5%), n-octacosyl acetate (M^+ 452, 41.2%) and n-triacontyl acetate (M^+ 480, 6.2%) respectively. The identity of the esters was further confirmed by their isolation and spectral analyses.

Compound B: Further elution with petroleum ether gave a yellow oily liquid, b.p. 227–28°/15 mm, identified as methyl ricinolate by chemical and spectral (ir⁵, pmr⁶, mass⁷) analyses and hydrolysis to the corresponding acid (ricinoleic acid).

Compound C: The petroleum ether–benzene (1 : 1) elution yielded colourless plates (MeOH), m.p. 138°; positive Liebermann–Burchard and TNM test; the acetate, m.p. 121–22°. Identification of the compound as β -sitosterol was made

through comparison of m.m.p., co-tlc, ir and pmr spectra.

Compound D: The eluate of petroleum ether–benzene (1 : 3) furnished colourless crystals (MeOH–Me₂CO), m.p. 141–42°; positive Liebermann–Burchard and TNM test; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 420, 1 040 (OH) and 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=C). The pmr and mass spectral data identified it as lanosterol which was further confirmed by m.m.p., co-tlc with authentic sample⁸ and preparation of the acetate, m.p. 132–33°.

The alcoholic extract on concentration under reduced pressure deposited KCl crystals. The mother liquor was reduced to red-brown syrupy mass and divided into methanol soluble and insoluble fractions. The methanol soluble part when chromatographed over silica gel, furnished the compounds E and F.

Compound E: Elution with EtOAc–MeOH (2 : 1) afforded yellow needles, m.p. 208–10°; positive TNM test; decolourised bromine and KMnO₄ solutions; green colour with alcoholic FeCl₃; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 220, 230sh, 285 and 325 nm. Its ir data revealed it to be caffeic acid which was further confirmed by preparation of the diacetate, m.p. 189–90° and the methyl ester, m.p. 151–52°.

Compound F: The eluate with EtOAc–MeOH (1 : 3) was crystallised as colourless crystals (MeOH), m.p. 236–37°, C₁₄H₁₆O₉ (M^+ 328); red colour with aqueous FeCl₃. It was identified as bergenin by comparison of its uv, ir, pmr and mass spectra with the reported data^{9,10} and preparation of the pentaacetate, m.p. 201–02°.

The methanol-insoluble part (water-soluble) gave positive Molisch test, and when subjected to ascending paper chromatography it revealed the presence of glucose, fructose and sucrose. The identity was further confirmed by co-pc with authentic samples.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the authorities, J. V. College, Baraut, for facilities; to Prof. K. K. Gandhi, Dr. U. S. Tiwari, I. I. T., New Delhi and Dr. Ramesh Chandra, Reader, Chemistry Department, Delhi University for spectral analyses.

References

1. S. B. MISHRA, "Bhav Prakash Nighanto", Chokhamba Sanskrit Series Office, Varanasi, 1966, p. 840.
2. R. N. CHOPRA, I. O. CHOPRA and S. L. NAYAR, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1966, p. 119.
3. R. JAIN and R. K. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 63, 581.
4. B. DINDA and M. K. SAHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 63, 764.